

AUTOMORPHISM GROUPS OF SUPEREXTENSIONS OF SEMIGROUPS

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The through study of various extensions of semigroups was started in [12] and continued in [1]-[10], [13]-[19]. The largest among these extensions is the semigroup $v(S)$ of all upfamilies on a semigroup S . A family \mathcal{M} of non-empty subsets of a set X is called *an upfamily* if for each set $A \in \mathcal{M}$ any subset $B \supset A$ of X belongs to \mathcal{M} . Each family \mathcal{B} of non-empty subsets of X generates the upfamily $\{A \subset X : \exists B \in \mathcal{B} (B \subset A)\}$ which we denote by $\langle B \subset X : B \in \mathcal{B} \rangle$. An upfamily \mathcal{F} that is closed under taking finite intersections is called a *filter*. A filter \mathcal{U} is called an *ultrafilter* if $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{F}$ for any filter \mathcal{F} containing \mathcal{U} . The family $\beta(X)$ of all ultrafilters on a set X is called the *Stone-Čech compactification* of X , see [20]. An ultrafilter $\langle \{x\} \rangle$, generated by a singleton $\{x\}$, $x \in X$, is called *principal*. Each point $x \in X$ is identified with the principal ultrafilter $\langle \{x\} \rangle$ generated by the singleton $\{x\}$, and hence we can consider $X \subset \beta(X) \subset v(X)$. It was shown in [12] that any associative binary operation $*$: $S \times S \rightarrow S$ can be extended to an associative binary operation $*$: $v(S) \times v(S) \rightarrow v(S)$ by the formula

$$\mathcal{L} * \mathcal{M} = \left\langle \bigcup_{a \in L} a * M_a : L \in \mathcal{L}, \{M_a\}_{a \in L} \subset \mathcal{M} \right\rangle$$

for upfamilies $\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{M} \in v(S)$. In this case the Stone-Čech compactification $\beta(S)$ is a subsemigroup of the semigroup $v(S)$. The semigroup $v(S)$ contains as subsemigroups many other important extensions of S . In particular, it contains the semigroup $\lambda(S)$ of maximal linked upfamilies, see [11, 12]. An upfamily \mathcal{L} of subsets of S is said to be *linked* if $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$ for all $A, B \in \mathcal{L}$. A linked upfamily \mathcal{M} of subsets of S is *maximal linked* if \mathcal{M} coincides with each linked upfamily \mathcal{L} on S that contains \mathcal{M} . It follows that $\beta(S)$ is a subsemigroup of $\lambda(S)$. The space $\lambda(S)$ is well-known in General and Categorical Topology as the *superextension* of S , see [21, 22].

Given a semigroup S we shall discuss the algebraic structure of the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(\lambda(S))$ of the superextension $\lambda(S)$ of S . We show that any automorphism of a semigroup S can be extended to an automorphism of its superextension $\lambda(S)$, and the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(\lambda(S))$ of the superextension $\lambda(S)$ of a semigroup S contains a subgroup, isomorphic to the group $\text{Aut}(S)$. We describe automorphism groups of superextensions of groups, finite monogenic semigroups, null semigroups, almost null semigroups, right zero semigroups, left zero semigroups and all three-element semigroups.

References

- [1] Banakh T., Gavrylyk V., *Algebra in superextension of groups, II: cancelativity and centers*, Algebra Discrete Math., **4**, 2008, 1–14.
- [2] Banakh T., Gavrylyk V., *Algebra in superextension of groups: minimal left ideals*, Mat. Stud., **31** (2), 2009, 142–148.
- [3] Banakh T., Gavrylyk V., *Extending binary operations to functor-spaces*, Carpathian Math. Publ., **1** (2), 2009, 113–126.
- [4] Banakh T., Gavrylyk V., *Algebra in the superextensions of twinic groups*, Dissertationes Math., **473**, 2010, 3–74.
- [5] Banakh T., Gavrylyk V., *Algebra in superextensions of semilattices*, Algebra Discrete Math., **13** (1), 2012, 26–42.
- [6] Banakh T., Gavrylyk V., *Algebra in superextensions of inverse semigroups*, Algebra Discrete Math., **13** (2), 2012, 147–168.
- [7] Banakh T., Gavrylyk V., *Characterizing semigroups with commutative superextensions*, Algebra Discrete Math., **17** (2), 2014, 161–192.
- [8] Banakh T., Gavrylyk V., *On structure of the semigroups of k -linked upfamilies on groups*, Asian-European J. Math., **10** (4), 2017, 1750083 [15 pages].
- [9] Banakh T., Gavrylyk V., *Automorphism groups of superextensions of groups*, Mat. Stud. **48** (2), 2017.
- [10] Banakh T., Gavrylyk V., Nykyforchyn O., *Algebra in superextensions of groups, I: zeros and commutativity*, Algebra Discrete Math., **3**, 2008, 1–29.
- [11] Gavrylyk V., *The spaces of inclusion hyperspaces over noncompact spaces*, Mat. Stud., **28** (1), 2007, 92–110.
- [12] Gavrylyk V., *Right-topological semigroup operations on inclusion hyperspaces*, Mat. Stud., **29** (1), 2008, 18–34.
- [13] Gavrylyk V., *On representation of semigroups of inclusion hyperspaces*, Carpathian Math. Publ., **2** (1), 2010, 24–34.
- [14] Gavrylyk V., *Superextensions of cyclic semigroups*, Carpathian Math. Publ., **5** (1), 2013, 36–43.
- [15] Gavrylyk V., *Semigroups of centered upfamilies on finite monogenic semigroups*, J. Algebra, Number Theory: Adv. App., **16** (2), 2016, 71–84.
- [16] Gavrylyk V., *Semigroups of centered upfamilies on groups*, Lobachevskii J. Math., **38** (3), 2017, 420–428.

- [17] Gavrylkiv V., *Superextensions of three-element semigroups*, Carpathian Math. Publ., **9** (1), 2017, 28–36.
- [18] Gavrylkiv V., *On the automorphism group of the superextension of a semigroup*, Mat. Stud., **48** (1), 2017, 3–13.
- [19] Gavrylkiv V., *Automorphisms of semigroups of k -linked upfamilies*, J. Math. Sci., 2018, article in press.
- [20] Hindman N., Strauss D., *Algebra in the Stone-Čech compactification*, de Gruyter (Berlin, New York, 1998).
- [21] J. van Mill, *Supercompactness and Wallman spaces*, Mathematical Centre Tracts, **85** (Amsterdam, 1977).
- [22] Verbeek A., *Superextensions of topological spaces*, Mathematical Centre Tracts, **41** (Amsterdam, 1972).